

ISic0135

I.Sicily inscription 0135

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble (giallo antico)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Auctario

2. Primigeni · f(ilio) ·

3. [vix(it) an]n(is) XXI ·

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini with slight changes based on the photograph

Translation (en)

To Auctarius, son of Primigenius. He lived 21 years.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175731

EDR 076859

EDCS 10900644

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1977.0335

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 54

Ferrua, A 1941. Analecta sicula. *Epigraphica*. 3: 252-270. At 260 no.17

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